

CAREER ANCHORS AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

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Abstract

The present study has been intended to know the relationship of career anchors and organizational commitment of faculty members in higher education. For this purpose, a sample of 319 faculty members from the three universities of Punjab viz. Punjabi University, Guru Nanak Dev University and Panjab University were selected. Similar and common faculties (Approximately one Professor, one Associate Professor and two Assistant Professors) from all the three universities were included in the study viz. Arts, Science, Pharmacy, Management and Business Administration, Computers, Languages and Law for collecting the data. The study was a descriptive survey research. Career Anchor Inventory by Delong (1982) and Organizational Commitment Questionnaire by Meyer and Allen (1997) were used by investigator for collection of data. Coefficient of correlation was used to find out the relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment. The results indicate that significant and positive relationship exists between career anchors and organizational commitment. As an employee engages in a career that is consistently aligned with her or his career anchor, work outcomes such as organizational commitment, job satisfaction, retention and career resilience are enhanced.

Keywords: *career anchors, organizational commitment*

Effectively attracting, developing, motivating, managing, retaining and committed employees have become a critical success factor for sustained organizational performance. As the world of work changes, it influences how employees view their careers. Employees are placing far more emphasis on satisfying their own individual demands and being more responsible for their own futures and careers. Since the responsibility for career management in a 'contemporary career' falls on the individual, self-insight is required when it comes to making the right choice. Individuals make better choices by knowing their career anchors.

The term career anchor was coined by Schein (1978) to describe the self-perceived pattern of values, needs, motivations, abilities, attitudes and talents that attract individuals to particular occupations. He suggested that the life experiences that people undergo give them a more accurate and stable 'career-self-concept', a construct which he labeled 'career anchor'.

Schein and van Maanen (2013) defined career anchor as a combination of perceived areas of competence, motives and values that you discover you would not give up if you faced a career decision that might not allow you to fulfill it.

According to Schein (1990), "One's career anchor can remain stable over time even without the opportunity to exercise the anchor. For example, a waitress who states she is 'really an actress'. The anchor can change if the individual obtains 'systematic experience and feedback' that make it impossible to maintain the career illusion. Continuing the example, the waitress though never wins any role and her performance fails to meet her own standards of an actress. Conversely, the anchor may remain stable if the individual does not internalize the constrain or if it is seen as temporary."

The concept of a career anchor emerged with an extensive study initiated by Schein in 1961 at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology which lasted for 12 years (Unal & Gizir, 2014). Career anchors are in fact values and skills that direct individual's career decisions directly. The concept of career anchors offers valuable insights in understanding diversity in career preferences and contemporary career patterns (Rodrigues & Guest, 2010).

The research conducted by Schein in the 1970s indicated that evolved self-concept is reflected in eight components of values, motives and basic needs namely technical competence, autonomy, service, identity/lifestyle, variety/pure challenge, managerial competence, security and creativity (Schein, 2006).

The most current implication of career anchor implies career development. In some cases, career anchor refers to a job or career which requires high level of training and education. In other cases, the term career anchor denotes a long-term commitment with broad psychological investment in a career or organization (Abbaspour, 2008; Ghalavandi et al., 2010). Individuals whose career development path permits the integration of personal needs, organization needs and the requirements of the job are more committed to the organization (Oreyzi Samani et. al., 2009). Organizational commitment is defined as a psychic attachment to the organization. Organizational commitment manifest in three understanding: 1-having

faith in organization and accepting its goals and values; 2-being inclined to strive for organization 3-wishing for remaining as a member of an organization (Ghafouri & Golparvar, 2010).

Meyer and Allen (1990) classified organizational commitment in terms of continuance, affective and normative commitment as mentioned under:

1. Affective commitment: Describes employee's emotional attachment to, identification with and involvement in the organization.
2. Normative Commitment: Reflects a feeling of obligation to continue employment.
3. Continuance Commitment: Relates to how much employees feel the need to stay in their organization.

Career Anchors and Organizational Commitment: A Research Review

Most of the individuals and organizations are not aware of team member's career anchors until team members are forced to make choices between team objectives and individual needs for meeting family, self-development or organizational commitment. Therefore, it is important for individual team members and organizations to become aware of these career anchors so that wise choices can be made when matching individuals to specific teams with particular goals and objectives. Stated differently, a more interconnected relationship exists when team member's career anchors are in balance with the organizational commitment, needs and expectations of the team (Schein, 1996). In this light, following are the studies indicating the relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment.

Schein (1978); Feldman and Bolino (1996); Ellison and Schreuder (2000); Sumner, Yage and Franke (2005) in a study explored the relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment and found that prior research shows a better 'fit' between individual's career anchors and work environment which can significantly benefit organizational outcomes such as work quantity and quality, job satisfaction, commitment to the organization and job stability.

Schein (1990) stressed that it is unrealistic to expect organizations to understand employees well enough to make valid career decisions for them. People must learn to manage their own careers. In this case, individuals should have their self-plan of career progression as well as increase their skills, knowledge and abilities (career anchors) while fulfilling their commitment to their organizations (Dessler, 2000; Dumitrescu, 2009).

Kristof (1996) investigated that person-organization fit i.e. fit between an individual's values as well as needs (career anchors) and organization's values as well as needs has a strong positive impact on organizational commitment and job satisfaction.

Ellison and Schreuder (2000); Van Vuuren and Fourie (2000); Hsu, Chen, Jiang and Klein (2003); Coetzee, Schreuder and Tladinyane (2007) recommended that as an employee engages in a career that is consistently aligned with her or his career anchor, work outcomes such as organizational commitment, job satisfaction, retention and career resilience are enhanced. For over 35 years, career researchers, corporations, career placement centers and individuals have used career anchor model to increase employee and organizational success.

Quesenberry (2006) investigated that there was a positive significant relationship between individual's career anchors and organizational commitment which was likely to be a result of self-perception, values and occupational motivation.

Rebecca (2007) found that there was a positive significant relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment.

Tladinyane (2007) investigated whether a relationship exists between organizational commitment and career anchors. The results indicated a probable relationship between organizational commitment and career anchors.

Abbaspour (2008); Ghalavandi (2010) stated that the current implication of career anchors implies career development. In some cases, career anchor refers to a job or career that requires high level of training and education. In other cases, the term career anchor denotes a long-term commitment with broad psychological investment in a career or an organization. Individuals whose career development path permits the integration of personal needs, organizational needs and the requirements of the job are more committed to the organization (Oreyzi Samani et al., 2009).

Zakerfard and Nuri (2008) investigated the relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment. They found that there was a positive significant relationship between them.

Oreyzi Samani et al. (2009) found that there was a positive significant relationship among career anchors, career authority and organizational commitment in a study of female and male employees occupying in research and development units of industrial firms.

Ghalavandi (2010) found that there was a positive significant relationship between *career anchor* components and *organizational commitment* components and also technical

functional competence, general managerial competence, autonomy, pure challenge and life style are significant predictors' of organizational commitment.

Lumley (2010) in a study on exploring the relationship between career anchors, organizational commitment and job satisfaction stressed that it seems important to explore the relationship between variables of career experiences, life satisfaction and job as well as career satisfaction in the contemporary career context. People's job and career satisfaction is increasingly recognized by organizations as important in retaining valuable and talented staff.

Amirtash, Mozafari, Mehri, Nasiri and Salehian (2011) found that a significant relationship was observed between career anchors and organizational commitment in a study of physical education and non-physical education faculties of Iran Provinces' Islamic Azad Universities.

Hasan, Azizollah and Yarmohammadzadeh (2012) investigated that there was a positive significant relationship between career anchor components and organizational commitment components and also technical functional competence, general managerial competence, autonomy, pure challenge and life style were significant predictors' of organizational commitment.

Clinton-Baker (2013) stated that there was a significant relationship between employees' career anchors and their organizational commitment. Career anchors were also found to be significantly related to organizational commitment with entrepreneurial creativity, lifestyle and service/dedication to a cause career anchors being the best predictors of these two variables.

Naghipour and Galavandi (2015) found that there was a positive significant relationship between career anchor components and organizational commitment components and also technical functional competence, general managerial competence, autonomy, pure challenge and life style were significant predictors' of organizational commitment.

Although the research literature provides evidence of the relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment, however, the investigator feels that an empirical study investigating the two variables is necessary. This issue appears to be more important when investigation into career anchors and organizational commitment was held within faculty members. Lack of sufficient research studies taking together, career anchors and organizational commitment and mixed results prompted the investigator to explore in this direction.

Justification of the Study

Organizations are often referred to as living entities with human capital that energizes the growth of the organization. Therefore, investing in recruiting the right employees and enhancing their skills can have a significant impact on the organizational function as a whole (Gatewood & Field, 2001). However, finding the right faculty members is only part of the answer to an organization's success. Another challenge is to maintain a challenging and motivating work environment. It is suggested that the origins of people's desire to work stems from factors such as emotional, attitudinal, social and economic consequences of their work. Therefore, each organization should pay much more attention to career anchors, especially when organization needs to assess the strengths and weaknesses of its human forces.

Schein (1990) also stressed that it is unrealistic to expect organizations to understand employees well enough to make valid career decisions for them. People must learn to manage their own careers. In this case, individuals should have their self-plan of career progression as well as increase their skills, knowledge and abilities (career anchors) while fulfilling their commitment to their organizations (Dessler, 2000; Dumitrescu, 2009).

Schein (1996) stated that most of the individuals and organizations are not aware of team member's career anchors until team members are forced to make choices between team objectives and individual needs for meeting family, self-development or organizational commitment. Therefore, it is important for individual team members and organizations to become aware of these career anchors so that wise choices can be made when matching individuals to specific teams with particular goals and objectives.

Based on their findings, Coetzee et al. (2007) suggested that organizations wishing to increase the commitment of their employees should strive for congruence between organizational rewards as well as the important motivations and values underlying their employees' career anchors. Their research is in line with that of Hsu et. al. (2003) and Kniveton (2004). It is with this;

Aim

The investigator aims to find out the relationship of career anchors with organizational commitment.

Hypothesis

Based on the above mentioned aim, following hypothesis was framed:

There exists significant relationship between components of career anchor and organizational commitment of faculty members teaching in different universities of Punjab

Method and Procedure

The present study employed descriptive survey research as it aimed at exploring the nature and distribution of variables and it was survey since it aimed at studying the present status of the variables under study as they were. In this study, organizational commitment was an independent variable whereas career anchor was a dependent variable.

Sample

For the present study, a sample of 319 faculty members from the three universities of Punjab viz. Punjabi University, Guru Nanak Dev University and Panjab University were selected. Similar and common faculties from all the three universities were included in the study viz. Arts, Science, Pharmacy, Management and Business Administration, Computers, Languages and Law for collecting the data. Approximately one Professor, one Associate Professor and two Assistant Professors were selected from all concerned departments. The technique of sampling was Multistage Random Sampling.

Instruments Used

Following instruments were used by the investigator in the present study:

- Career Anchor Inventory by Delong (1982) adapted by the investigator
- Organizational Commitment Questionnaire developed by Meyer and Allen (1997)

Statistical Techniques Employed

To analyze the data, coefficient of correlation was used to find out the relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment.

Results and Discussion

The eight components of career anchors as dependent variables were separately correlated with independent variable of organizational commitment as well as its three dimensions viz. affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Correlation Matrix showing Career Anchors and Organizational Commitment in case of Total Sample (N = 319)

Variable	TCC M	AUTN	SRVC	IDNT	VART	MGC O	SCRT	CRTV	CRAN
AFCO	0.267*	0.257*	0.435*	0.276*	0.353*	0.355*	0.166*	0.432*	0.424*
CNCM	0.063	0.165*	0.086	0.300*	0.194*	0.206*	0.407*	0.117*	0.261*
NMCM	0.175*	0.170*	0.234*	0.354*	0.264*	0.281*	0.337*	0.239*	0.340*
ORGC	0.249*	0.292*	0.375*	0.448*	0.398*	0.413*	0.436*	0.391*	0.502*

Note: **: Significant at 0.05 level ($r = 0.110$)
*: Significant at 0.01 level ($r = 0.144$)

Discussion Based on Table 1

In case of affective commitment, as per the Table 1 that barring a few exceptions, association between various other pairs of the variables was direct (i.e. positive) and highly significant (at 0.01 level). In a certain combination, the extent of association was at a relatively lower level such as security and affective commitment ($r = 0.166$, $p = 0.0028$). Thus, in general, it is concluded that for total sample, various pairs of the study variables were significantly but positively associated with each other.

However, in case of continuance commitment, as per the Table 1 that barring a few exceptions, association between various other pairs of the variables was direct (i.e. positive) and highly significant (at 0.01 level). The extent of association was at a relatively lower level in case of autonomy and continuance commitment ($r = 0.165$, $p = 0.0031$) and in case of creativity and continuance commitment ($r = 0.117$, $p = 0.0367$), significant and positive correlation exists at 0.05 level of significance. Notably, the only unassociated pairs of variables were observed to be: technical competence and continuance commitment ($r = 0.063$, $p = 0.2619$) and service and continuance commitment ($r = 0.086$, $p = 0.1253$). Autonomy, identity, variety, managerial competence and security were found to have significant but positive correlation with continuance commitment (at 0.01 level) in this study. Thus, in general, it is concluded that for total sample, various pairs of the study variables were significantly but positively associated with each other.

As per the Table 1 that barring a few exceptions, association between various other pairs of the variables was direct (i.e. positive) and highly significant (at 0.01 level) in case of normative commitment. In certain combinations, the extent of association was at a relatively

lower level. Such combinations were: technical competence and normative commitment ($r = 0.175$, $p = 0.0017$); autonomy and normative commitment ($r = 0.170$, $p = 0.0023$). Thus, in general, it is concluded that for total sample, various pairs of the study variables were significantly but positively associated with each other.

Moreover, in case of organizational commitment, all the components of career anchor were found to have significant but positive correlation with organizational commitment. The pair of variables was very strongly and directly associated with each other. In other words, there exists a very strong tendency for the two variables to move in the same direction. Since the values of r between various variables were far higher than even the 0.01 critical value, therefore, it is concluded that the association between the pair of variables was highly significant (at 0.01 level).

Thus, the null hypothesis stating ‘There exists significant relationship between components of career anchor and organizational commitment of faculty members teaching in different universities of Punjab’ was accepted in the present study.

These findings are in consonance with findings of Schein (1978, 1990, 1996); Feldman and Bolino (1996); Kristof (1996); Dessler (2000); Ellison and Schreuder (2000); Van Vuuren and Fourie (2000); Hsu, Chen, Jiang and Klein (2003); Sumner, Yage and Franke (2005); Quesenberry (2006); Coetzee, Schreuder and Tladinyane (2007); Rebecca (2007); Abbaspour (2008); Zakerfard and Nuri (2008); Dumitrescu (2009); Oreyzi Samani et al. (2009); BaharFard and Javaheri (2010); Ghalavandi (2010); Lumley (2010); Amirtash, Mozafari, Mehri, Nasiri and Salehian (2011); Hasan, Azizollah and Yarmohammadzadeh (2012); Clinton-Baker (2013); Naghipour and Galavandi (2015) who found that significant but positive relationship exists between career anchors and organizational commitment.

Conclusions of the Study

The results of the present study indicate that all the components of career anchor were found to have significant and positive correlation with organizational commitment and its dimensions *viz.* affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

Educational Implications

The present study would be useful for Policy Makers, University Managements and Principals. As career anchors develop and appear over a sequence of professional development through which individuals evaluate themselves through various positions of work (Lee & Wong, 2004) thus, policymakers should financially support educators and

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universities for developing relationships with different organizations so that these organizations offer different opportunities, activities and positions for faculty members to assess their career anchors and then, help those faculty members to choose and develop the type of career that suits their type of anchor. Hence, this study has implications for individuals seeking to better understand their careers anchors as it provides insights into the tasks, rewards and environmental aspects most likely to provide satisfaction at work.

The study suggests them the need to identify career anchors of academic faculty which will further help the organizations to tailor and focus career initiatives more successfully. If the academic faculty remain in a job that is not congruent with their career anchors and repress their motivations, they seek to achieve the missing elements of their anchor through outside work interests or by withdrawing commitment, which has obvious implications for organizations. Therefore,

- There should be flexible reward systems, promotion systems and recognition systems to address the differing needs of the individuals. For example, people with a lifestyle anchor are likely to place a high value on flexible benefits whereas people with a security/stability anchor will be more biased towards pension schemes and steady incremental pay scales.
- Individuals need to discover their career anchors and plan their future career strategies. They should negotiate with their employing organization regarding future assignments.
- The organization should utilize information about career anchor hierarchies in connection with biographical variables to plan future developmental opportunities for academic faculty.
- Topics such as career management could be included in the continuous education programme of the university faculty members.
- Organizations should realize that the fit between employees' internal values, their organizational commitment, emotional intelligence and job satisfaction is the key to their employability satisfaction.
- Management should introduce the concept of career anchors to their employees as an integral part of career development discussions. Career discussions should be organized on how employee's career anchors influence their organizational commitment, emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. Such discussions could encourage them to

explore the motives and values underlying their dominant career anchors.

- Human resource management practices in organizations should find the way to realize career guidance programmes by helping individuals to identify their dominant career anchors as well as career paths that they could pursue.
- The employees' career anchors, their internal motivations should be directed correctly that their organizations are included in this process as well as support them and that the employees' career desires are not depleted by the organization-based factors. For this, it is necessary to prepare career steps for advancement in the organizations, to develop association activities in which employees will make connections between their occupations, to support employees' personal development, to provide a career-based conflict by controlling the internal conflicts and provide career opportunities to the employees in different departments with multiple career centres by switching from a progressive organization structure to a stagnant organization structure, if the organization structure is suitable.

The findings contribute new knowledge to the field of career psychology and may be used to inform human resource practitioners concerned with optimizing person-job fit and the employability, job and career satisfaction of employees. In the light of the turbulent world of work context, career counselors may also find the results useful in facilitating proactive career behavior among employees.

References

- Abbaspour, A. (2008). *Advanced human resource management, (Approaches, Process and Functions)*, Tehran: Samt Publication (In Persian). In Ghalavandi, H.; Arbabisarjou, A.; Yarmohammadzadeh, P.; Soltanzadeh, V.; Iman, S. & Sokooti, N. (2012). *Relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment among faculty members. Journal of Studies in Education*, 2(1), 61.
- Amirtash, A. M.; Mozafari, S. A. A.; Mehri, K.; Nasiri, M. & Salehian, M. H. (2011). *Comparison of career anchors and organizational commitment among physical education and non-physical education faculties of Iran Islamic Azad Universities. Scholars Research Library*, 2(5), 232-239.
- BaharFard, A. & Javaheri, M. (2010). *The study of organizational equality, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. Bimonthly Police Human Development*, 7(28), 25-118 (In Persian). In Ghalavandi H.; Arbabisarjou, A.; Yarmohammadzadeh, P.; Soltanzadeh, V.; Iman, S. & Sokooti, N. (2012). *Relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment among faculty members. Journal of Studies in Education*, 2(1), 63.
- Clinton-Baker, M. (2013). *The relationship between career anchors, organizational commitment and turnover intention, Master's Dissertation, University of South Africa.*

- Coetzee, M.; Schreuder, D. & Tladinyane, R. (2007). *Organizational commitment and its relation to career anchors*. *Southern African Business Review*, 11(1), 65-86.
- DeLong, T. J. (1982). *The Career Orientation Inventory: Assessing the career needs and values of educators*. Unpublished manuscript.
- Dessler, G. (2000). *Human resource management*, Prentice-Hall, New Jersey.^[1]
- Dumitrescu, D. M. (2009). *Human resources profile in the virtual organization based on the career anchors of Edgar Schein*. *Annals of DAAM for 2009 and Proceedings of the 20th International DAAAM Symposium*, 20(1), 7-55.
- Ellison, J. A. & Schreuder, A. M. G. (2000). *The relation between career anchors, occupational types and job satisfaction of midcareer employees*. *South African Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 26(2), 1-6.
- Feldman, D. C. & Bolino, M. C. (1996). *Careers within careers: Reconceptualizing the nature of career anchors and their consequences*. *Human Resource Management Review*, 6(2), 89-112. doi: 10.1016/S1053-4822(96)90014-5
- Gatewood, R. & Field, H. (2001). *Human resource selection*. Harcourt Brace and Company, Orlando.
- Ghafouri, M. R. & Golparvar, M. (2010). *A survey of relationship between organizational justice and organizational commitment among staff of Isfahan Municipality*. *Psychological Studies*, 5(4), 129-148 (In Persian). In Ghalavandi, H.; Arbabisarjou, A.; Yarmohammadzadeh, P.; Soltanzadeh, V.; Iman, S. & Sokooti, N. (2012). *Relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment among faculty members*. *Journal of Studies in Education*, 2(1), 60.
- Ghalavandi, H. (2010). *Determination of relationship between quality of work life and career anchors with organizational performance perspective of faculty members in Tabriz, Urmia and Ardabil Universities*. In Arbabisarjou, A.; Yarmohammadzadeh, P.; Soltanzadeh, V.; Iman, S. & Sokooti, N. (2012). *Relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment among faculty members*. *Journal of Studies in Education*, 2(1), 59-60.
- Ghalavandi, H.; Rajaeepour, S.; Molavi, H. & Sharif, S. M. (2010). *A study of the relationship between quality of work life and career anchors with organizational performance perspective among faculty members of the Universities*. *Journal of Psychology*, 5(19), 113-134.
- Hasan, G.; Azizollah, A. & Yarmohammadzadeh, P. (2012). *Relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment among faculty members*. *Journal of Studies in Education*, 2(1), 58-71.
- Hsu, M. K.; Chen, H. G.; Jiang, J. J. & Klein, G. (2003). *Career satisfaction for managerial and technical anchored Information System personnel in later career stages*. *Database for Advances in Information Systems*, 34(4), 64-72.
- Kniveton, B. H. (2004). *Managerial career anchors in a changing business environment*. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 28(7), 564-563.
- Kristof, A. L. (1996). *Person-organization fit: An integrative review of its conceptualizations, measurement, and implications*. *Personnel Psychology*, 49(1), 1-49. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1996.tb01790.x>
- Lumley, E. (2010). *Exploring the relationship between career anchors, job satisfaction and organizational commitment*, Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of South Africa, Pretoria. Retrieved on 19 November 2011, from <http://uir.unisa.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10500/3455/dissertation_lumley_e.pdf?sequence=1>.

- Meyer, J. P. & Allen, N. J. (1990). *The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization*. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63(1), 1-18.
- Meyer, J. P. & Allen, N. J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace: Theory, research and Application*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Naghipour, K. & Galavandi, H. (2015). *The relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment*. *International Journal of Educational and Psychological Researches*, 1(4), 241-245. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2395-2296.163938>
- Oreyzi Samani, H. R.; Zakerfard, M. & Nuri, A. (2009). *The relationship of career with job power and organizational commitment: A case study of male and female personal of research and development units of industrial companies*. *Woman's Studies Sociological and Psychological*, 7(1), 69-93 (In Persian). In Ghalavandi, H.; Arbabisarjou, A.; Yarmohammadzadeh, P.; Soltanzadeh, V.; Iman, S. & Sokooti, N. (2012). *Relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment among faculty members*. *Journal of Studies in Education*, 2(1), 60.
- Quesenberry, J. L. (2006). *Career anchors and organizational culture: A study of woman in the IT workforce*, *Sigmis cporb proceeding of the ACM Sigmis CPR conferences*, 342-344.
- Rebecca, T. (2007). *The relationship between career anchors and organizational commitment*, M.A. Dissertation, University of South Africa.
- Rodrigues, R. & Guest, D. (2010). *Career anchors of professional workers: Extending Schein's framework*. Symposium paper presented at the 27th International Congress for Applied Psychology, 16 July, Melbourne, Australia.
- Schein, E. H. (1978). *Career dynamics: Matching individual and organizational needs*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Schein, E. H. (1990). *Career anchors: Discovering your real values*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass Pfeiffer. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/03090590410549984>
- Schein, E. H. (1996). *Career anchors revised: Implications for career development in the 21st century*. *The Academy of Management Executive*, 10(4), 80-88.
- Schein, E. H. (2006). *Career anchors self-assessment (3rd ed.)*. San Francisco: Pfeiffer.
- Schein, E. H. & van Maanen, J. (2013). *Career anchors (self-assessment): The changing nature of work and careers*, John Wiley and Sons, San Francisco.
- Sumner, M.; Yage, S. & Franke, D. (2005). *Career orientation and organizational commitment of IT personnel*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 2005 ACM SIGMIS CPR conference on Computer personnel research.
- Unal, B. & Gizir, S. (2014). *An investigation on the dominant career anchors of faculty members: The case of Mersin University*. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 14(5), 1759-1765, doi: 10.12738/estp.2014.5.2110
- Van Vuuren, L. J. & Fourie, C. (2000). *Career anchors and career resilience: Supplementary constructs*. *South African Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 26(3), 15-20.
- Zakerfard, M. S. & Nuri, A. G. (2008). *Relation between career and organizational commitment*, *The First Crenation Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, University of Esfahan.